

NEW NOSOLOGICAL MODEL OF CHRONIC ENDOMETRITIS

Dante Roberto Salatino ★

About the author

★Dante Roberto Salatino is a researcher of the Institute of Philosophy and of the Institute of Linguistics - Lecturer in the General Psychology Department – Lecturer in the Philosophical Aspects of Physical-Mathematical Science Department - Faculty of Philosophy and Letters - Teacher and Researcher in Artificial Intelligence in the Mechatronics Career - Faculty of Engineering - National University of Cuyo - Email for correspondence: dantesalatino@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this work was to investigate a new nosological model of chronic disease, in this case, Endometritis, to provide other elements for its diagnosis and treatment. The method used to obtain the information consisted of the analysis of the relationships between the fundamental elements that determine the chronic entity, following the principles of the Transcursive Logic. The results obtained in previous investigations warn about some questions to be clarified. The supposed "cure" of infection (bacterial endometritis) suggests that we will get a live birth from all pregnancies, but only half of the women who have the infection will become pregnant. On the other hand, the normalization only of the immune state that alters the infection would result in a high rate of spontaneous abortions. Even when everything is normal, the abortion rate is not negligible, nor is the amount of other pathology that accompanies these pregnancies, such as premature births. It was found that if we take the endometrium, that is, the internal lining of epithelial tissue of the uterus where the

embryo implantation takes place, as a system in itself, we can better approach the achievement of our aims. The latter implies taking into account, on the one hand, its microbiota/microbiome, a symbiotic community of microorganisms that, housed in the uterine cavity, constitutes a first defensive barrier; and on the other, the aspects that define your local immune system. A "dysbiosis", that is, an altered microbiota, can give rise to a state of chronic inflammation, even in the absence of pathogenic germs, and which may have originated, e.g., in some previous antibiotic treatment. The investigations carried out concluded that modeling allows considering chronic endometritis as the confluence of the structural, functional, and systemic reactions that an infection can cause. Therefore, its diagnosis is possible even if the usual evidence of its presence does not exist, and the treatment can be extended beyond the traditional (antibiotics, corticosteroids, bone marrow stimulants, etc.), such as the use of cultures. of mesenchymal stem cells to regenerate a healthy endometrium.

Key words: Chronic inflammation, nosological models, microbiota/microbiome, stem cells, transcurssive logic.

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1.0. INTRODUCTION

Nosology consists of a systematization of diseases given the knowledge that one has of them, based on theoretical assumptions about the nature of the pathological processes that characterize them.

The purpose of this work was the elaboration of a new nosological model of Chronic Endometritis (CE), to adjust its diagnosis and treatment, approaching the disease through the methodological guidelines provided by the Transcurssive Logic (TL) (Salatino, 2019).

Chronic Endometritis, as a nosological entity, is a subtle and continuous inflammation of the endometrium, that is, of the internal lining of epithelial tissue of the uterus where the embryo implantation takes place (Kimura et al., 2019).

As a consequence of the above, their presence plays an important role in the recurrent loss of pregnancies (Romero, Espinoza and Mazor, 2004; Johnston-Mac Ananny et

al., 2010; McQueen et al., 2015; Tersoglio and Salatino, 2015; Cicinelli, 2017; Vitagliano et al., 2018; Kimura et al., 2019; Hirata et al., 2020). The prevalence of CE, in women affected by repeated implantation failure (FRI), is in the order of 37% (Vitagliano et al., 2017). High implantation rates have been reported, after CE has been cured, compared to those women where the disease was not cured (76% vs. 59%) (Tersoglio & Salatino, 2015). The fact that the disease has been cured, that is, that cultures for different germs are negative, that no histopathological elements are indicating chronic infection, or that other indices certify this condition, does not necessarily mean that their negative influence on pregnancy has finished.

2.0. STATE OF THE ART

It was demonstrated that both the normalization of endometrial histopathology and endometrial NK cells (a type of white blood cell present in the endometrium, also in the blood), constitute individual predictors of clinical pregnancy (Figure 1) (Tersoglio and Salatino, 2019a).

		HISTOPATHOLOGY	
		0	1
NK/Li	1	EC = 70% NV = 40% AE = 30% NE = 30%	EC = 83% NV = 78% AE = 05% NE = 17%
	0	EC = 00% NV = 00% AE = 00% NE = 100%	EC = 50% NV = 50% AE = 00% NE = 50%

Figure 1 PREGNANCY OUTCOMES ACCORDING TO PREDICTORS

References: CE: clinical pregnancy - NV: live birth
 AE: miscarriage - NE: no pregnancy - 1: normal - 0: abnormal

The previous figure shows us that in the best case (group 11), that is, where the two predictors were normalized, we obtained 78% of live births, but there were 5% of spontaneous abortions and 17% that did not become pregnant. In the worst case (group 00), both abnormal predictors, no pregnancies were obtained. But, in the intermediate groups, the results were not as categorical. When only the NK were normalized (group 01), only 40% of live births were obtained, and 30% of spontaneous abortions. Whereas, when only histopathology was normalized (group 10), there were 50% of live births and no abortion.

The previous results alert us to some issues. The supposed "cure" of infection (bacterial endometritis) suggests that we will get a live birth from all pregnancies, but that only half of the women who have the infection will become pregnant. On the other hand, the normalization of the immune state alone (normalization of the NK), would result in a high rate of spontaneous abortions, and consequently, fewer live births than the previous case. Even when everything is normalized, the miscarriage rate is not negligible, nor is the amount of other pathologies that accompany these pregnancies, such as premature births.

It is clear then that, with the supposed elimination of an infection, or a supposed stabilization of the immune state of the endometrium, it is not enough to definitively exclude the consequences on fertilization that produces the chronic inflammation. Trying to determine what are the factors that we are not considering to solve this problem is the main reason for this work.

3.0. THE ENDOMETRIUM AS A SYSTEM

Since the beginning of the 20th century, and for more than 50 years, there was consensus that a healthy uterine cavity was a sterile cavity. In the late 1980s, using appropriate culture media, the presence of uterine bacteria began to be reported, even in healthy asymptomatic women (Baker et al., 2018). In fact, and even though the fetus is sterile, as soon as it is born, its cavities open to the environment begin to be plagued by germs.

These microorganisms that accompany the human being throughout his life are known by the generic name of "microbiota", and maintain, in health conditions, a balanced symbiotic relationship with their carrier. The number of microorganisms that inhabit a human body is estimated to be ten times greater than the total amount of its body cells, although they only weigh 200 grams (Madigan et al., 2019).

On the other hand, all the members of the microbiota have their genetic code. This genome is called a "microbiome". The human genes are approximately 23,000, while the genes of the microbiota reach 3,000,000, that is, 130 times more numerous (Noce et al., 2014). The above figures mean that the microbiota and its genes must be considered as one more organ of our body, which is also unique and unrepeatable, like a fingerprint.

To consider the endometrium as a system and object of our study, we must take into account, on the one hand, its microbiota/microbiome and on the other, the aspects that define its local immune system.

Figure 2 shows the relationships, which, in our opinion, present the fundamental elements that define the endometrium as a true system.

Figure 2 ENDOMETRIAL PAU

References: DP: passive defense - DA: active defense

genus: species of a bacterium - phenotype: external manifestation of the set of hereditary characters -

genotype: set of genes characteristic of each species

For a long time, the group of microorganisms that coexist symbiotically in our intestinal tract was called "intestinal flora". However, this name is inaccurate since "flora" refers to plant life and we know that these microorganisms are bacteria, fungi, and yeasts, the functioning of which has no relation to that of plants. That is why the most precise and scientifically accepted name of microbiota has been adopted today to name this micro-ecosystem.

Now, what is the difference between microbiota and microbiome? As we already mentioned, the microbiota is the set of microorganisms that coexist symbiotically with our organism. The cells of our microbiota outnumber the number of human cells by a ratio of 10 to 1. All of these cells also have their genetic code, which, although different from ours, is closely related to our health. It is for the total set of germs of our microbiota that scientists have adopted the name of microbiome.

The set of genes contained in the human microbiome could serve to identify us as individuals as if it were a fingerprint. According to scientists, each microbiome has distinctive characteristics of the host organism, therefore, it is possible to identify a person from the analysis of the genes that house their microbiome.

Figure 3 gives detail of how an animal's immune system works. We see that faced with the aggression of any pathogen; the animal has two immune subsystems. An innate immunity that is present in all animals, whose main characteristics focus on its rapid response, and the possibility of recognizing a wide range of aggressors, using a small set of receptors. There are two types of defenses in this modality. The "external defenses" made up of the skin, mucous membranes, and secretions. Instead, the "internal defenses" are represented by phagocytic cells (they eat the harmful cells); the natural killer cells (that we have already mentioned, and then we will analyze in more detail); antimicrobial proteins, and an inflammatory response generated as a defense against invasion.

Figure 3 IMMUNE SYSTEM IN ANIMALS
(Adapted from Reece et al, 2018)

The other immune modality is adaptive immunity, which is the heritage only of vertebrates and is characterized by responding slowly, using a large group of receptors to recognize a particular pathogen agent.

3.1. ALTERATIONS OF THE DYNAMIC BALANCE OF MICROBIOTA / MICROBIOME / LOCAL IMMUNITY

In recent years, has increased research focused on improving our knowledge of the delicate balance between microbial and immune agents that coexist at the endometrial level (D'Ippolito et al., 2018). Although this complex system constitutes protection against the risk of infection, in certain circumstances, it can lead to it, and with it, spoil the normal implantation of an embryo.

The establishment of a chronic inflammatory condition, such as endometritis, for example, depends on several factors. One of them is the alteration of the dynamic balance microbiota/microbiome, or what is known as dysbiosis (Hedayat and Lapraz, 2019, p. 77).

This imbalance of the microbiota concerning the needs of the organism, obeys three basic reasons (Ibidem, p. 87): 1) insufficiency of the microbiota, 2) loss of diversity of the constituent microorganisms, and 3) the presence of competitors pathogenic germs (infection). The predominant normal microorganism in the reproductive system, during pregnancy, is Lactobacillus, and it is supposed to constitute a natural barrier that prevents the entry of pathogenic germs.

When the natural barrier is altered or disappears, a series of events are triggered that make up a dysbiosis episode, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 DYSBIOTIC PAU

References: TLR: Toll-like receptors (relate innate immune responses to adaptive ones - recognizing germs and viruses, initiating the inflammatory process)

In the first place, due to the lack of recognition of the aggressors, bacterial growth is favored (01); then, genomic instability of the epithelial cells occurs (11), decreasing the external defenses given the detachment that affects the skin and mucosa cells (10); Besides, the autophagy process is altered, which is how an immune cell destroys a germ, engulfing it. All this results in an absence of the inflammatory process (00) that accompanies all aggression, and therefore, the process goes unnoticed by the immune system. Although sometimes, this inflammation occurs, it does not trigger an adequate immune response, and then, a chronic inflammatory episode appears, like the one we are considering.

On the other hand, the endometrium deactivates the immune reaction that should take place when the embryo, a product of the union of a mother's cell, with a heterologous tissue (the paternal sperm), tries to nest. That is, the entry of a foreign tissue does not generate a rejection. In this way, the endometrium constitutes a true system that plays a central role in uterine immune surveillance.

How does the local immune system work?

Figure 5 guides us in this regard.

Figure 5 IMMUNITARY PAU
(Modified from Dranoff, 2004, p. 18)

With a didactic objective, we are going to suppose that the immune system works in the same way that the Ministry of Security of any country does, whose reason of being, of course, is to decrease the number of infractions to the established norm, which in the case at hand would be to discern the proper from the strange and attack the latter.

Thus, we have offenders (invaders), a police force that guards the streets (blood) in search of offenders, a dungeon to temporarily house detainees until they are identified, a prosecutor who takes the case to the judge, who is the one who determines the guilt and sentence the death penalty. Also, there is a special body (the natural killers, belonging to innate immunity) whose mission is to sentence and execute the offender without prior judgment, given their dangerousness.

The "police" represents innate immunity, as it is the first line of defense against infection, and it acts in two ways to stop the invader, or at a distance, using soluble substances (taser pistols) called "complement", or melee fight. This last operation is carried out by specific cells (granulocytes, mast cells, macrophages, dendritic cells, and NK cells - See Figure 5). This form of defense is fast and effective since they can recognize (through their "identikit"), effectively, a large number of germs, and orchestrate an immediate inflammatory reaction. On the other hand, adaptive immunity is represented by the entire apparatus in charge of administering justice, which is why, as in judicial administrative activity, everything is slower here, since there is no direct action, but rather through antibodies generated in the "history of previous attacks" (the equivalent of a criminal's record) of the invaders, a record kept by special white blood cells: T cells and B cells.

There are three types of T cells: 1) T_{CD4} or helper T lymphocytes that activate other cells so that they either "present" the antigen to the effector cells (the case of B cells, or the "prosecutor" of the cause), or to execute the aggressor without prior judgment (macrophages, killer lymphocytes or T_{NK}); 2) T_{CD8} or cytotoxic, responsible for the executing function of cellular immunity, neutralizing the invader and destroying it; and 3) $T_{\gamma\delta}$ and T_{NK} that share their functions between innate and adaptive immunity, and are frankly enforcers, but always with prior activation ("execution order" issued by the judge).

Finally, as a fundamental part of the immune system, we have the "Major Histocompatibility Complex" (the court and its judges). In this complex (in court)

there is a “place” (cell or dungeon) where the suspect is placed until finding out his antecedents. Cells B (prosecutor) present the case (antigen), to the "judge", who evaluates, making recognition of the aggressor, if dictate sentence, giving the activation order to the cells that are responsible for the execution of the inmate. All this meticulous mechanism can be approached from the Transcursive Logic because the structural and functional relationships that all its members maintain constitute a PAU, as can be seen in Figure 5.

4.0. CHRONIC ENDOMETRITIS

To detect bacteria and viruses, the immune system has a series of receptors called "pattern recognizers" (or RRP), and they are expressed through antigen-presenting cells, such as dendritic cells and macrophages. Their basic mode of action is reflected in Figure 6.

Figure 6 PAU OF RRP

References: Transmembrane/endo cellular: location of the receptor concerning the cell membrane - NLR: DNA detector of viruses and bacteria - TLR: recognizes components of the bacterial membrane - CLR: recognizes different species of fungi - RLR: detects viral RNA.

NLR receptors, also called “inflammasomes”, are in charge of unleashing the inflammatory cascade and are key in the regulation of the microbiome (Suresh and Mosser, 2013; D’Ippolito et al., 2018). TLR receptors are the ones that give the first signal to trigger the inflammatory cascade. CLR receptors (Plato et al., 2015) recognize all types of fungus, in addition to collaborating with TLRs, and this collaboration has been used therapeutically in the treatment of fungal infections, so common in immunosuppressed patients (cancer treatment, transplant recipients), victims of HIV), as well as those caused by some bacteria and viruses. All this complex mechanism, in the endometrium, has a particular behavior. Thus, for example, in the presence of a possible infection, TLR receptors attract NK cells (uNK or uterine NK cells) and macrophages to develop the required immune response. The uNKs are a heterogeneous population that arises either from local parents or from peripheral NK cells (residing in the blood). The absolute number of these cells

increases during ovulation, although it remains at a constant rate throughout the menstrual cycle (30%) compared to other white blood cells. But, during pregnancy, this proportion increases to 70%, from which it is inferred that the uNK is involved in the success of the implantation processes and the progress of the pregnancy, but also in its failure when the mechanism is corrupt (D'Ippolito et al., 2018).

Sometimes, the expression of the genes that encode the proteins involved in the inflammatory process is altered (from pattern recognizers), this triggers a series of disorders in the functioning of the different groups of white blood cells, consequently altering the secretion of antibodies that turn against the organism itself (unknown), also increasing the inflammasomes and the release of substances that attack the cells, now not invasive, but from the normal endometrium (Op. Cit.).

Regardless of whether or not there has been a previous infection, this failure in recognition, especially by TLR receptors (associated with CLR), alters the implantation process and produces chronic endometritis that no longer depends on a germ, a fungus or a virus, but of an imbalance in the immune response.

Local immunity can also be altered in the presence of dysbiosis (Hedayat and Lapraz, 2019, p. 79).

As a consequence, the implantation rate falls, and therefore, of pregnancies; in those pregnancies that manage to start, the inflamed endometrium cannot support them, with the total number of live births decreasing in all cases.

5.0. CONCLUSIONS

The definition of a new nosological model of chronic endometritis, as conceived in this work, is based on the basic aspects that enable an episode of endometritis, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 PAU OF ENDOMETRITIS

According to Figure 7, when a pathogen reaches the endometrium, housed within the uterus, a series of chained phenomena occur. First, a structural reaction appears that is felt in the uterine organ; then, a functional reaction that alters the behavior of the endometrial epithelium, bringing consequences both in the menstrual regime and in the case of the possibility of a new pregnancy. On the other hand, the infection produces a systemic reaction (that is, it involves the entire organism), when the immune response is triggered to try to defend against the aggression and its consequences. The immune reaction that occurs in the endometrium can be abnormal and lead to chronic inflammation, as we have seen.

Considering the foregoing, it is possible to make the diagnosis of chronic endometritis, although the usual evidence does not exist, by discovering, through a careful analysis of the local immune system, some type of deviation from its normal functioning.

On the other hand, the possibility arises of not abandoning attempts to achieve a pregnancy that ends successfully, in those cases of repeated implantation failure where traditional treatment (antibiotics, corticosteroids, bone marrow stimulants, etc.) has not given Outcome. Very recent research (Tersoglio, Tersoglio, Salatino, et al., 2019b) shows that reactivation of mesenchymal stem cells can regenerate a weakened endometrium, such as what remains, for example, when chronic endometritis has developed.

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